

Fig. 2

periodically through S as otherwise the benzene will be pushed down too much into the horizontal portion and carried away in bulk. This discharge of colour and the liberation of hydrogen and oxygen clearly show that chemical reaction can take place in the intermediate zone during electrolysis.

Reaction in the intermediate zone is more strikingly shown if only benzene without any dye is used to start with and the electrolysis is continued for a long time. It would be observed in the course of a day or two of current conduction that benzene gets slowly reacted out to form a brown soluble substance which spreads out from the middle zone to the anode; this portion DBA then becomes progressively more brown as the current is continued, and a frothy deposit of an aromatic compound slowly gets formed near the top of the anolyte. If the electrolysis is continued for a week or two the whole solution in DBA extending from the bottom of the cathode limb right along the whole anode limb becomes deep brown in colour. Evidently, a slow but intense reaction goes on in the intermediate zone to produce a soluble substance from benzene. The substance formed can be easily isolated by evaporation to dryness and it appears to be a resinous polyphenol soluble in water. By using a slightly modified apparatus (a simple U-tube), similar resinous phenolic product is obtained from chlorobenzene and also from nitrobenzene, aniline etc. with rapid liberation of HCl in the case of C_6H_5Cl , HNO_2 in the case of $C_6H_5NO_2$, etc. These liquids being heavier than water are merely have to be left at the bottom as a small layer in the path of the current. It is evident that under the above condition the intermediate zone can by no means be considered a zone of no reactivity only offering passage to the migrating ions which carry the current; it is a seat of intense chemical activity even decomposing highly stable compounds such as chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, etc., particularly under conditions of anomalous electrolysis. It appears that this novel observation is somehow associated with non-Faradaic electrolysis reported by the author² and is probably due to electrical migration of active

free radicals which attack the benzene or chlorobenzene in the intermediate zone.

Further work is in progress and detailed results will be reported later. Thanks are due to Sri Prithwis Kumar Basu for essential experimental assistance.

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Spectrophotometric Studies on complex Formation of 5-Nitro-Salicylic Acid (5NSA) with Copper(II)

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC investigation showed the existence of two complexes between copper (II) and 5NSA. Application of Job, mole ratio and slope ratio methods indicated the formation of 1 : 1 complex at pH 4.0. The formation constant of this 1 : 1 complex has been determined employing Job, mole ratio and Foley and Anderson methods. Formation of 1 : 2 complex has also been indicated above pH 7.0. Its dissociation constant has been determined spectrophotometrically. The solution absorption spectra indicated a distorted octahedral structure for copper(II)-5-nitrosalicylate complexes.

As a part of a series of experiments on complex formation of 5-nitrosalicylic acid (5NSA) with various metal ions in solution¹⁻⁴, a spectrophotometric study of its reaction with copper(II) ions has been made. The results have been given below.

Experimental

5NSA was prepared by the method as described by Hirway⁵. Copper(II)-perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolving E. Merck sample of copper(II)-carbonate in dilute perchloric acid (Merck, G.R.). It was estimated iodometrically. All other chemicals used were B.D.H. Analar.

pH of the solutions were measured with 'Polymetron CL-41' pH-meter.

Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using 'Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20' spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on colour of the system copper(II)-5NSA was first tested. In Fig. 1 are shown three typical absorption curves taken on Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20' spectrophotometer containing 0.025M copper(II)-perchlorate and 0.05M 5NSA at different pH values (pH 5.0 for curve I, 6.1 for II and 10.9 for III). From a series of such curves at values from pH 2.3 to 11.2 it was found that curves for solutions above pH 7.0 were of the type of III with an absorption peak at 665 nm. Those for solutions of pH less than 5.0 were of the type such as I, with maximum absorption at ≈ 750 nm or above. Between pH 5.0 and 7.0 there was apparently a transition from type I to III, as illustrated by the curve II.

The above study suggested the existence of two different complexes between copper(II) and 5NSA. Studies on composition were then made both at pH 4.0 and 7.4.

Complex at pH 4.0 :

(a) *Spectral Characteristics of the Complex* : Mixtures containing various proportions of copper(II) and 5NSA (pH 4.0), 5NSA being always in much excess over copper(II), were prepared and kept for half an hour to attain equilibrium. Absorbance of solutions, at different wavelengths, was measured in each case. In all cases maximum absorption occurred at 750 nm. Further, under these conditions Beer's law has been found to be valid. The molar extinction co-efficients of the complex and copper(II)-perchlorate were found to be 48 and 10.04 respectively at 750 nm.

(b) *Stoichiometry of the Complex* : The ratio of copper(II) to 5NSA in the complex was determined by Job's method⁶. A series of solutions was prepared with varying ratios of copper(II) and 5NSA but with the total molarity of the two being constant at pH 4.0. Absorption measurements were made at 650, 700 and 750 nm. A typical set of data is recorded in Table 1.

The difference, \bar{D} , between the observed optical density of each solution and that which would be given by the original reagent if no association occurred is plotted against the ratio $[Cu]/[Cu]+[5NSA]$ as shown in Fig. 2, curve II to V, clearly indicating the formation of 1:1 complex. At lower pHs the probability of any other higher complex existing in the solution is very small.

Formation of 1:1 complex has been further confirmed by Mole ratio⁷ and Slope ratio⁸ methods.

TABLE I—COPPER(II)-5-NITROSALICYLATE

$\frac{[Cu]}{[Cu]+[5NSA]}$	\bar{D} Cu(II) = 5NSA = 0.0166M pH 4.0			\bar{D} Cu(II) = 5NSA = 0.025M pH 7.4
	700 nm	750 nm	650 nm	650 nm
0.1	0.068	0.068	0.062	0.188
0.2	0.108	0.115	0.105	0.260
0.3	0.148	0.178	0.136	0.378
0.4	0.178	0.205	0.152	0.325
0.5	0.192	0.232	0.166	0.255
0.6	0.185	0.218	0.153	0.162
0.7	0.180	0.210	0.148	0.075
0.8	0.168	0.192	0.129	0.032
0.9	0.155	0.172	0.115	0.032

Fig. 1. Copper(II)-5NSA.

Complex at pH 7.4 :

Similar determination by Job's method⁶ was made at pH 7.4. A typical set of data is recorded in Table I and the result is shown in Fig. 2, curve I. The curve indicates that in this pH region the complex formed is 1 : 2.

Evaluation of the formation constants :

The formation constant (K) of 1 : 1 complex was calculated by Foley and Anderson⁹, Job⁶ and mole ratio⁷ methods and recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANT OF Cu(II)-5NSA

Method	$K\alpha$	$K = 1/K\alpha$	$\log K$
Foley and Anderson	2.65×10^{-3}	3.773×10^2	2.5769
Mole ratio	2.76×10^{-3}	3.623×10^2	2.5691
Job	3.62×10^{-3}	3.333×10^2	2.5228

The formation constant for 1 : 2 complex could not be determined so well because the data are not sufficiently accurate to permit correction for effect of precipitation, dissociation to 1 : 1 complex and similar factors. However, the sharp peak at the maximum of the curve I, Fig. 2 indicates that the dissociation is small. A rough value of the dissociation 1 : 2 complex determined from its molar extinction coefficient (50) was found to be 1.25×10^{-8} .

Fig. 2. Copper(II)-5NSA.

Structure of the complex :

Of many interesting aspects in the complex chemistry of the 3d⁹ copper(II) ion, one certainly is the large extent of distortion that its complexes suffer due to Jahn-Teller effect^{10,11}. As a result most of copper(II) complexes are either distorted octahedral or distorted tetrahedral. In general copper(II) complexes in tetrahedral, planar or octahedral co-ordination should exhibit ideally three absorption bands¹². However, commonly this is seldom observed and mostly a broad asymmetric band is observed.

The solution absorption spectra of Cu(II)-5NSA, in our case, provide a broad absorption band around 16,000 cm⁻¹. The frequency of this absorption is certainly at a much higher energy than those for tetrahedral or distorted tetrahedral structures¹³ and is again somewhat lower for square planar¹⁴ stereochemistry. It is, therefore, only plausible to invoke a distorted octahedral structure for Cu(II)-5NSA complex.

The close resemblance in reactions of Cu(II) with salicylic acid and 5NSA indicates that linkage occur with the carboxyl and phenolic groups.

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